

Need For Uniqueness in Clothing among Females (A Case Study of District: Khairpur Mir`S Sind, Pakistan)

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Abstract

The purpose of this research article is to recognize the need-for-uniqueness in clothing among female of district: khairpur sindh, Pakistan. Research high-lights that the majority of females are interested in fashionable outfits in order to look themselves stylish, beautiful & unique than others. Most of the females want to wears outfits that others do not have. Fashions have an effect on the personality of a person either male or female but research indicates that the females are more conscious about their dressing. Our dressing fluent that how we think our selves & how we perceive ourselves as well as how we desire to be considered by other people. When we purchase outfits we purchase exclusivity for ourselves.

Key words: Need, uniqueness, fashion, clothes, purchases, shopping.

Introduction

The center of attention of this research is to identify the need for uniqueness in clothing among female. Consumer decision making for latest manufactured goods adoption is one of the most enthusiastically researched areas in the social sciences in terms of the number of publications (E.M. R. , 1983). Fashion industry earns billion of dollars every year. Millions of the people use fashion products around the world everyone wants to look different, unique and stylish person can look different and stylish by using fashionable products the markets become global, A large number of consumers affected by the prompt growing fashion industry. Uniqueness & Fashion affect our society & our culture is also affected by the fashion. Similarly it replicates how individuals describe themselves. People have a propensity to associate fashion with clothing and accessories. Fashion and uniqueness can be originated in approximately every human activity. (M.R & N.J, 2007) Now a day's most worthy costumers are placing more views addicted to their shopping. Consumers are rethinking about their purchases as an alternative of buying numerous; low priced stylish products such as: clothing, bags, and shoes. (Sherman, 2009) According to (A & G., 2011) luxury product market grows on worldwide level for the duration from 1995 to 2007. Particularly, the yearly expansion rate for luxury product market was the eleven percent in the period of 1995 to 1999 this period was also known as the time of the luxury brands' detonation and the 1% throughout the three years of time period from 2000 to 2003 the well-being magnificence business diligence & the eight percent in between 2004 & 2007 the expansion of the magnificence business diligence into the new up-and-coming market. (Q, A., & G., 2010,2011) The need for uniqueness is depend on the

number of dimensions which includes bustle performance altitude (C.R & H.L., 1980) evaluation of Scarcity (h.L., J.C., R.L., & D., 1971) attitudes & way of life apprehended (C.R & H.L., 1980) way of social networks build (M, j., & M, 1977), and the utilization activities (E.L & G, 1968). The need for uniqueness in consumer shopping products is aspiration-leaning situation, The potency and strength of this need is different from person to person. Personality differences in the intensity of this need have a lot of reasons. These reasons includes: personality differences in the desire for uniqueness (C.R & H.L., 1980), position aspiration (T & R, 1989) and acquisitiveness (R.W, 1985).

Literature review:

Shopping is a buying activity which is performed by people and it is women who go for shopping in the large extent. (R.R, 1999) To illustrate shopping as a gender activity can conversely be a generalization. In spite of this reality, still there are a number of common differences among the male and female shopping patterns. An ordinary stereotype concerning men and the shopping is when men go into a retail store, purchase their desire product, and after that they promptly leave. Shopping is for extended connected with the household products. Mostly Women perceive outfits as a represent for-self-identity, while gentleman focuses more on the practical benefits of clothing. (McGrath, "M.A" and "C" perception and actuality of men purchase behaviour. 2001)

Our dressing articulate that how we think our selves & how we perceive ourselves as well as how we desire to be considered by other people. When we purchase outfits we purchase exclusivity for ourselves. (M., 2008).

Dressing represents an significant communal component

of the person's well-being. All the way through the exact choice for dressing it is probable for a person to pick up their self-esteem moreover recognition by further citizens. ((ed), 2009) Identity & societal role appears by individual's preference for clothing & accessories. Dressing work as a sign which indicates the, social group, status, adherence & personality of a person. (J., 2009)

Individual's shopping behavior demonstrate their attitude, taste and values to other people. Uniqueness in fashion products could associated with all the characteristics of a person's appearance which provides value to them on different stages. Uniqueness in fashion products become an imperative & consequential activity for the people who take interest in it. (L. & R., 2009).

Clothes purchasing is considered entertaining, pleasing and satisfying. Female shopping for garments is a severely individual accountability. Female claim for shopping more than male and considered shopping as an important activity. In view of the fact that female consider shopping like amazing and frivolous so it's imperative to highlight the empirical traits for shopping. (R.R, 1999)

Female mostly find in shopping agreeable than male and they possess more optimistic approach towards the social interaction that frequently followed by the buying course of action. Female mostly attached with shopping in their free times. Shopping plays a psychological, emotional and representative role in women's life and women utilize their more time and money on shopping than men. Furthermore female is typically a window-shopper. (Kuruvilla, S.J, & S., 2009).

When consumers buys any product and approve a precise product, at that time consumer communicates their aspiration which is linked with the class of individuals and also supposed to consume the precised product. (I. & Prendergast, 2000)

According to (G, 2002) there is a connection between the innovativeness and the need for uniqueness. According to the Fromkin point of view "need for uniqueness" 'shove the people to differentiate themselves by the possession of uncommon products. (G, 2002) Suggested some of the consequences for the need for uniqueness these consequences are: The lack of interest inside the response of other people to their unique ideas or acts; the aspiration for not to follow the rules all the times; and the readiness to openly preserve one's opinion.

The exterior look of a person's need for uniqueness that is the result of a social evaluation process, which depends on the person's self-apparent level of uniqueness comparative to other people. Throughout this social evaluation process a person evaluates themselves with the other peoples groups or individuals thus

provided themselves with framework of reference with future decision making activities can take place. The process consists to compare the current state with various ideal states distinct by the person, depend on the potency of their need for uniqueness. Person's self-apparent level of uniqueness is the indication of how intimately individual perceives herself/himself to look like others. (DJ & HB., 1995)

According to (DJ & HB., 1995) need- for -uniqueness might apparent in the purchasing of fashionable clothes. If people distinguish themselves as they have inadequate personal distinctiveness than they will be encouraged to follow the behavior such as purchasing fashionable outfits which possibly will have to put right this disagreeable condition. As well, people with strong needs for the uniqueness would more probable to desire purchaser choices which might be out looked as the latest thing/nontraditional. Like purchasing new fashionable outfits from somewhere by which the need-for-uniqueness could be manifest. Such as a boutique.

Methodology:

The purpose behind this research is to explore the Need for Uniqueness in Female of district: Khairpur Sind Pakistan, particularly in Clothing. The research employed a case study of College/university girls, Working women as well as few housewives in District: Khairpur Sind Pakistan. Information unruffled from nearly 70 respondents, include women around the age of 18 to above 30 and the crate study include the questions of "how" and "to what extent" women in particular place have need for uniqueness.

In the designed case study loom, questionnaires were used as crucial data assortment tool. The limited ecological locality, quantity of respondents available and quality of appraise respondents, the uncomplicated casual sampling technique be preferential as a result the study articles are worn like a derived data assortment, facts composed on or after the 70 respondents be universal for the quantity of willing women. The scholars individually managed the opinion poll with the assist of a small number of girls in college, hostels and housewives in the selected area, Respondents were given of 5-7 days time to complete the questionnaires. In accumulation up to take advantage of questionnaire, some interviews were also conducted through the random female. The unruffled information was shortened, implicit and programmed, by means of the Software 'Statistical Package Science Solutions 16.0 (SPSS)' for factor generation groping and factor investigation. Expressive figures are worn to analyze, illustrate and understand the information. The issue examination was also worn to establish whether a

relationship existed connecting the collision of need for uniqueness in clothing.

Result:

The research indicates that the females in Khairpur prefer to have something unique and they have the strong need for uniqueness particularly in clothing. Women here want to become trend follower specially the young girls (18-28) want to look different from others hence they prefer uniqueness in their shopping stuff. While most of the elder women don't really care about the uniqueness they rather prefer to have things in which they feel comfortable. Also the elder women in Khairpur feels more comfortable to the things they are already using from years. Young College girls are brand conscious and the opinions of other about them matters them. Girls do care what others comment about them which makes them to choose the clothes that also matches the other stuff like accessories and bags. Most of the replies show that there is the strong need-for- Uniqueness.

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction sums-of-squared loadings		
	Total	%of "Variance"	"Cumulative" %	Total	% of "Variance"	"Cumulative" %
1	9.027	36.109	36.109	9.027	36.109	36.109
2	4.950	19.801	55.910	4.950	19.801	55.910
3	3.518	14.073	69.983	3.518	14.073	69.983
4	1.653	6.612	76.595	1.653	6.612	76.595
5	1.197	4.788	81.862	1.197	4.788	81.383
6	1.120	4.479	85.862	1.120	4.479	85.862
7	.899	3.597	89.459			
8	.644	2.578	92.037			
9	.423	1.690	93.727			
10	.304	1.216	94.943			
11	.263	1.052	95.995			
12	.193	.771	96.766			
13	.176	.705	97.471			
14	.148	.591	98.062			
15	.099	.395	98.547			
16	.082	.329	98.786			
17	.73	.293	99.078			
18	.057	.229	99.308			
19	.044	.175	99.483			
20	.034	.136	99.619			
21	.033	.133	99.751			
22	.025	.100	99.852			
23	.017	.067	99.919			
24	.011	.045	99.964			
25	.009	.036	100.000			

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
I prefer being ___ different from other women around.	.785	-.524	.090	.050	.009	-.057
Being distinctive is ___important to me.	.715	.181	.562	-.001	-.194	.021
I have___ uniqueness in everything I purchase.	.302	.182	-.800	.157	.072	.307
I___intentionally do things to make myself different from women around me.	.378	.768	.134	.201	.111	.160
I select uncommon products as way of telling other women that I'm different.	-.303	-.652	-.088	.501	.505	.137
When dressing I have something dared to be different in ways that others are likely to disapprove.	-.455	.255	.690	-.123	.060	.258
I avoid products and brands have already being accepted and purchased by the average female customers.	.394	.205	-.756	-.053	-.242	-.330
As far as I'm concerned when I come to the product i buy in situation in which I use them, customers rules are made to be broken.	-.211	.557	-.321	-.099	.447	-.377
When products or brands i like become extremely popular i lose interest in them.	.296	-.884	-.162	-.176	.072	-.082
I have sometimes purchased unusual products and brands as a way to create a mole distinctive personal image.	.670	-.350	.198	.046	-.057	-.141
I sometimes look for one-of-a-kind products or brands so that I create a style that is all my own.	.647	-.337	.157	.580	.149	.003
I am ___ attracted to unique objects.	.888	.320	-.042	-.060	-.161	-.166
I often combine possession in such a way that I create a personal image that can't be duplicated.	.795	-.527	.075	-.127	.002	-.085
Often when buying merchandise in important Cole is to find something that communicate my uniqueness.	.786	.244	.428	.077	.088	.169
I enjoyed having things that others do not have.	-.777	-.150	.459	-.115	.059	.254
I often try to find a more interesting version of run-of-the mill products because I enjoy being original.	.881	-.355	.188	-.086	.088	.035
I actively seek to develop my						

personal uniqueness by buying special products and brands.	.582	.225	-.404	.044	.256	.270
I will try new products even if I have not heard of it before.						
It sometimes bothers me quite that I can't afford to buy all the things I'd like.	-.763	.498	.037	.114	-.215	.021
	.485	.274	.343	.453	.281	-.142

Limitations:

This research is limited to female in District: Khairpur Sind Pakistan. Furthermore the focus of this study is only on the need for uniqueness in clothing, there are no other factors involved in this research.

Conclusion:

This research-article recommends a number of noteworthy contributions of the females of District: Khairpur, Sind Pakistan. According to them clothing is an significant part of feminine personality it builds women's personality. The feminine approach towards purchasing unique-and-fashionable outfits seems very optimistic and positive. Unique-and-fashionable clothes favored by females in-order-to make stronger self-admiration. Most of the females enjoying the outfits that others do not have. Females often combine possession in such a way that they create a personal image that can't copied by others. The products become very popular most of the female lose their interest towards the product. Some females avoid purchasing the product which is already purchased and used by other females.

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